

Does age affect organizational commitment and individual work performance?

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to examine the effect of age on organizational commitment and individual work performance. To broaden and deepen the concepts of the study, literature was reviewed. The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design. The population of the study is the employees of the institution. Questionnaires were used to gather the data and weighted mean and Pearson r were used to interpret and analyze the data. The study found that overall, there is no correlation between age and organizational commitment and individual work performance. However, there is a significant correlation between age and affective commitment of the employees which suggests that the older they become, the more affectionate they become to the institution.

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Introduction

Research on organizational commitment has persisted over decades, remaining a focal point for organizational and behavioral researchers. The ongoing discourse surrounding its definition and dimensions underscores its enduring relevance in management. Scholars emphasize its pivotal role in organizational success, with commitment serving

as a key determinant of organizational effectiveness (Herrera & Heras-Rosas, 2021; Steinhaus & Perry, 1996; Schein, 1970; Steers, 1975).

Employee performance, crucial for organizational effectiveness, is influenced by various behaviors, including task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993; Podsakoff et al., 2000; Motowidlo & Van Scotter, 1994; Zhou, 2020; Van Eerde, 2016). Such behaviors, in turn, impact organizational performance (Siddiqui, 2014; Tarmidi & Arsjah, 2019).

Organizational commitment and performance are intertwined variables, influenced by organizational factors like wages and job satisfaction (Alamelu et al., 2015; Kose & Kose, 2017; Triwahyuni, 2017). Age, among other factors, also plays a role. Recent studies suggest that age influences organizational commitment (Ngatuni & Gasengayire, 2021).

Despite differing perspectives, age's impact on work performance remains contested. While cognitive abilities may decline with age, studies show mixed results regarding its effect on productivity (Lam & Lee, 2006; Rietzschel et al., 2016; Avolio et al., 1990; Li et al., 2022; Converso et al., 2018; Czaja, 1995; Viviani et al., 2021).

Given the diverse age demographics within organizations like the Divine Word College of Laoag, understanding age's influence on organizational commitment and performance is crucial. With limited literature on this topic, this study aims to contribute to this discussion.

The study comprises several phases: introduction, literature review, research methodology, data presentation and analysis, and results and discussion. Each phase is designed to deepen understanding and establish theories pertinent to the investigation.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to enhance comprehension of the study's concepts and theories, thereby elucidating the research problems under investigation. A thematic presentation of the reviewed literature allows for a structured analysis and synthesis of key insights.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Age and Work

Age plays a significant role in workforce dynamics, shaping the parameters of employment selection. Both minimum and maximum age requirements are commonplace across organizations. The ILO Convention 138 (1973) underscores the importance of setting a minimum age for employment to safeguard the well-being of young workers, stipulating it not be less than 18 years old. Similarly, the Philippine Labour Code, in Article 137, delineates provisions for the employment of individuals aged 15 to 18, with stringent regulations to ensure their safety and welfare. These regulations aim to prevent the employment of minors in hazardous or detrimental work environments, as determined by labor authorities.

The Philippine Labor Code stipulates a mandatory retirement age of 65 (ZGLAW, 2018), signaling the end of employment for individuals upon reaching this age. However, between the ages of 18 and 65, no universal policy compels all corporations to accept or reject applicants solely based on age. Despite this, many organizations impose age limits in their selection processes, a practice that may conflict with R.A. No: 10911, which aims to eliminate age discrimination in employment.

What remains lacking in both the ILO regulations and the Philippine Labor Code is the underlying philosophy behind age limits in employment. Understanding this philosophy would shed light on the rationale behind such limits and their relevance in employment selection processes. Therefore, delving into the philosophical aspects of age in the context of work is essential for grasping the significance of age requirements in employment practices.

Age, as defined by both the Cambridge and Merriam-Webster Dictionaries, refers to the length of existence or the time of life at which particular qualifications, powers, or capacities arise or rest. This concept aligns closely with Baltes' (1987) idea that as individuals age, they experience gains and losses across various life domains while being influenced by contextual and developmental factors. Rietzschel (2016) further illustrates this by highlighting the decline in working memory, processing speed, attention, and the ability to process new information with age. Park and Festini (2017) corroborate this, linking aging to cognitive decline, particularly in working memory capacity.

The impact of age on cognitive performance and task execution is evident in studies by Li et al. (2022), Just and Carpenter (1992), Daneman and Carpenter (1980), and Nye et al. (2022). These studies indicate that age-related differences in cognitive abilities affect task performance, contributing to the formulation of age-related policies in companies (Perry & Bourhis, 2006). In today's technologically integrated work environments, age requirements in the selection process gain significance, particularly in fields like information technology, where older employees may face challenges adapting to evolving technologies due to declining cognitive functions (Li et al., 2022; Gilinsky & Judd, 1994; Vaughan & Laborde, 2021).

Organizational Commitment

The concept of commitment, particularly organizational commitment, exhibits variation among researchers and dictionary definitions. For instance, the Cambridge Dictionary (n.d) defines commitment as the "willingness to give time and energy to a job, activity, or belief," while Dictionary.com by Oxford Languages characterizes it as "dedication to a cause, activity, or obligation that restricts freedom of action." Despite nuanced differences, both emphasize dedicating oneself to a cause or activity.

However, these definitions lack the psychological dimensions integral to commitment. Leonard (2009) elucidates this by defining commitment as "a state of mind that binds individuals and organizations to certain behaviors," emphasizing the psychological contract with the institution. Similarly, Ajayi and Muraina (2016) stress the self-identification aspect, defining commitment as "the extent to which an individual identifies with the organization." Ceylan (2020) further underscores this psychological bond, defining commitment as "aligning time and interests with the organization based on personal wishes and beliefs."

These definitions collectively highlight three critical characteristics of commitment: emotional attachment fostering a loyal relationship with the organization, self-identification with the organizational values, and investing time and interest in organizational goals. They underscore the emotional aspect of commitment, emphasizing the profound attachment individuals feel towards their organizations.

Meyer and Allen (1991) describe organizational commitment as a psychological state defining the employee's relationship with the organization and influencing decisions to continue or discontinue membership. This aligns with Porter, Steers, Mowday, and Boulian's (1974) perspective, viewing commitment as the strength of an individual's identification and involvement in the organization. Similarly, Idris and Manganaro (2017) emphasize psychological identification in their definition of organizational commitment.

Porter and Lawer (1965), as cited by Herrera and Heras-Rosas (2021), conceptualize organizational commitment as employees' desire to exert high effort and remain loyal to the institution's objectives and values. This sentiment is echoed by Greenberg and Baron (2008), who define commitment as the extent to which employees identify with and demonstrate commitment to the organization.

Organizational commitment, therefore, encompasses the psychological contract individuals hold with the organization. Rousseau (1995) elaborates on this, defining the psychological contract as individuals' beliefs regarding reciprocal obligations and benefits in an exchange relationship. This exchange entails relational contracts, characterized by emotional exchange and loyalty based on expectations such as promotion and job security, and transactional contracts driven by economic exchanges, where salary and benefits meet expectations (MacNeil, 1985).

Numerous studies, including those by Fischer and Mansell (2009), Mathieu and Zajac (1990), Meyer et al. (2002), and Solinger et al. (2008), have explored the impact of organizational commitment on individual behavior. Their findings consistently demonstrate a strong correlation between organizational commitment and occupational commitment, job satisfaction, and job involvement. Employees exhibiting higher organizational commitment levels are less inclined to leave the organization, show reduced absenteeism, engage in organizational citizenship behavior, and experience improved well-being (Angle & Perry, 1981; Mathieu & Zajac, 1990; Meyer et al., 2002; Solinger et al., 2008).

Dimensions of Organizational Commitment: Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment.

Scholars concur that organizational commitment comprises multiple dimensions, including attitudinal, behavioral, and motivational aspects. Morrow (1993) identified attitude and behavior as key dimensions, with attitude encompassing positive evaluative judgments reflecting attachment, identification, and loyalty to the organization (Miller, 2003). Meyer, Allen, and Gellatly (1990) further emphasize attitude as a positive cognitive and affective stance towards the organization, mirrored in behavior as suggested by Ajzen (1993).

Organizational commitment manifests when individuals are dedicated to their tasks (Best, 1994) and to the groups within the organization (Reicher, 1985). This psychological bond is evident in active participation in group activities (O'Reilly, 1989) and a sense of job involvement, loyalty, and belief in organizational values (Miller & Lee, 2001). Employees' acceptance of organizational goals and willingness to exert effort underscore this psychological connection.

Scholars have proposed multidimensional perspectives on organizational commitment, often with overlapping dimensions. Meyer and Allen (1997) identified three dimensions: affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Affective commitment reflects an employee's emotional attachment to the organization, fostering sustained involvement (Lowry, 1973). Employees with high affective commitment exert more effort for organizational benefit (Johnson & Chang, 2006), driven by intrinsic motivation and a desire for loyalty (Becker et al., 1996; Meyer et al., 2004). Continuance commitment emerges from a cost-benefit analysis favoring retention over departure, based on perceived personal investment and limited alternatives (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Meyer & Allen, 1984).

Normative commitment arises from a sense of obligation to the organization (Allen & Meyer, 1990), rooted in moral and legal considerations (Muhammad et al., 2021). O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) highlight compliance, identification, and internalization dimensions. Compliance pertains to the relationship between employee contribution and extrinsic rewards, akin to continuance commitment. Identification and internalization capture emotional attachment and valuation of organizational goals, akin to affective commitment.

Similarly, Balfour and Wechsler (1996) delineate identification, affiliation, and exchange dimensions. Identification reflects pride in the organization, akin to affective commitment, while affiliation denotes attachment to coworkers and the organization, akin to affective commitment. Exchange commitment, akin to continuance commitment, emerges from perceived recognition of efforts with benefits. These dimensions offer nuanced insights into employees' varied commitments to their organizations.

O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) and Wechsler (1996) encapsulate three dimensions that align with Meyer and Allen's (1997) framework. Thus, this paper adopts Meyer and Allen's (1997) three dimensions—*affective organizational commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment*—as the foundation for investigation.

The Dimensions of Individual Work Performance

Individual work performance is a paramount concern for management, as organizational success hinges upon it. Regular monitoring and evaluation of employee performance are essential to detect deviations from objectives promptly (Armstrong, 2015; Murphy, 2019). However, the lack of consensus on the definition of work performance among scholars leads to confusion about the dimensions to be evaluated (Dallas, 2005).

Motowidlo (2003) defines job performance as the total expected value to the organization of discrete behavioral episodes carried out by an individual over a specified period. Gulino (2022) and Turanligil (2019) strengthen this definition, describing work performance as the total execution of assigned tasks by a worker. Their definitions underscore work performance as the output of behavioral activities.

Recent scholars uphold Campbell's (1990) definition of individual work performance as "behaviors or actions relevant to organizational goals" (Campbell, 1990). Work performance is perceived as a means to achieve both individual and organizational objectives, focusing on behavioral aspects rather than outcomes (Campbell, 1990). Kasemsap (2016) defines work performance as "work-related activities expected of an employee and their execution," while Ahmad (2011) sees it as "the ability of workers to perform their job." Similarly, Karapinar (2017) describes work performance as "an appraisal report assessing how well employees fulfill job-related activities." These definitions underscore work performance strictly as behavior-based, independent of outcomes, aligning with Campbell's perspective (2013b). They apply across various occupations, with dimensions limited to behavior.

Drawing from Campbell's (1990) definitions, work performance evaluation now strictly centers on behavioral dimensions, excluding outputs. However, the question of what constitutes work performance remains, necessitating identification for measurement (Viswesvaran, 2002). Campbell et al. (2001) initially outlined five dimensions of work performance in the military, later expanded to eight in 1993. Borman and Motowidlo (1993, 1997) condensed these into task and contextual performance, while Organ (1988) introduced organizational citizenship behavior. Bennett & Robinson (2000), Berry et al. (2007), Gruys & Sackett (2003), and Dalal (2005) added counterproductive work behavior. Koopmans et al. (2011, 2014) proposed task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior, with the latter study introducing adaptive performance. However, this paper focuses solely on the three dimensions outlined by Koopmans et al. (2011), as they are deemed relevant for the investigation.

Task performance, as defined by Borman & Motowidlo (1993), and cited by Silong et al. (2013), refers to the effectiveness in carrying out activities crucial to the organization's "technical core," either directly or indirectly. This competency, also termed task proficiency or technical core by Campbell (1990), involves behaviors directly impacting task completion and organizational processes (Harrison, Newman, & Roth, 2006). Conversely, contextual performance, defined by Doğru (2019), entails positive behaviors such as volunteering for extra duties and aiding coworkers beyond job requirements, identified as organizational citizenship behavior by Organ (1988). While not obligatory, these behaviors contribute to the organizational environment, supporting task performance. Studies indicate a relationship between contextual performance, task performance, and overall effectiveness (Diaz-Vilela et al., 2015; Griffin et al., 2001).

Counterproductive work behavior (CWB), as defined by Fox and Spector (2005), encompasses negative actions hindering organizational objectives and harming individuals within the organization (Robinson & Bennett, 1995). These behaviors, including abuse, sabotage, and theft (Spector et al., 2006 as cited by Ispas & Borman, 2015), target both the organization and its members. Within workgroups, CWB may manifest as *laissez-faire leadership, norm*

violations, and relationship disruption (Braun & Hentschel, 2015), ultimately aiming to thwart organizational success through various deliberate actions.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Allan and Meyer (1990), cited by Abdullah, (2011), Koopmans, et al., (2011).

Figure 1: The framework explains the influence of age on the organizational commitment and individual work performance of employees.

Statement of the Problems

The study evaluated the effect of the age of the employees on their organizational commitment and individual work performance. It answered the following questions:

1. What are the different ages of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag?
2. What is the organizational commitment of the employees?
3. What is the individual work performance of employees?
4. Is there a relationship between age and organizational commitment?
5. Is there a relationship between age and individual work performance?

Assumption

The study assumes that age contributes significantly to organizational commitment and individual work performance.

Hypothesis

Cognitive ability is a function of age which may lead to a potential job performance deficit. Rietzschel, et al., (2016) argued that an employee's working memory, processing speed, attention and ability to process new information steadily decline with age throughout an individual's life. It also affects significantly overall organizational affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment (Ngatuni & Gasengayire, 2021).

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study limits its investigation to the effect of age on organizational commitment and individual work performance among the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag.

Research Methodology

In line with scientific standards, this research adheres to a defined research methodology. Wilkinson (2000) and Leedy (1974) assert that research methodology provides a structured approach to inquiry, employing specific methods to collect, analyze, and interpret data relevant to the research topic. Thus, the study implements various investigative methods, including research design, data gathering instruments, population selection, study locale, data collection procedures, and statistical data analysis techniques.

Research Design of the Study

The study employs a descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design. According to Ariola (2006), descriptive correlational research aims to depict relationships among variables without inferring causation. Conversely, descriptive research seeks to depict a population, situation, or phenomenon, often through profiling and frequency distribution. In essence, it addresses "what," "when," "how," and "where," rather than "why" questions (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag. The college is located in Laoag City, the capital of Ilocos Norte.

Population

The study encompasses employees of the college as its respondents. Given the limited number of employees, a total enumeration sampling approach was employed, encompassing all faculty and staff members from the college as respondents.

Data gathering instruments

The study utilized validated questionnaires developed by Allen and Meyer (1990), as referenced by Abdullah (2011), to assess organizational commitment. Additionally, questionnaires on work performance, developed by Koopmans et al. (2012), were employed. Permission to use these questionnaires was obtained from the respective authors.

Data Gathering Procedures

To uphold the scientific integrity of the research, data collection commenced following approval from the Presidents of various colleges. The researcher initiated this process by sending letters to the presidents for their endorsement. Once approved, the questionnaires were distributed by a designated representative of the researcher. Subsequently, representatives from each institution collected the data and submitted it to the researcher for tabulation.

Ethical Procedures

The study proceeded after thorough examination and approval by the research ethics committee. Their evaluation ensured that the paper adhered to ethical standards and did not pose any harm to human life or the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed. The weighted mean facilitated the assessment of employees' self-efficacy, work performance, and work environment, while the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) quantified the relationship between age, organizational commitment, and individual work performance. The resulting values will be interpreted using the following descriptive ranges:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree/ Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree / High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree/ Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part presents data and is followed by an analysis. The data presentation follows the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1: What are the different ages of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag?

Table 1. Age of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag (n=120)

AGE OF THE EMPLOYEES	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
25 – 30	38	31.66
31 – 35	35	29.16
36 – 40	22	18.33
41 - 45	5	4.17
46 – 50	8	6.67
51 - 55	5	4.17
56 - 60	2	1.67
61 – 65	5	4.17

The institution's workforce is largely composed of young employees aged 25-30 (31.66%) and 31-35 (29.16%). Middle-aged employees aged 36-40 represent the second largest group at 18.33%. Only a small percentage, 6.67%, falls within the 46-50 age bracket. Few employees remain until optional (60) or compulsory (65) retirement ages, with most leaving around age 40 or after gaining experience with the institution.

Problem 2: What is the organizational commitment of the employees?

Table 2. Organizational commitment of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag (n=120)

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
A. Affective Commitment		
1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization	3.82	A/H
2. I feel as if this organization's problems are my own	3.72	A/H

3.	I feel like 'part of my family at this organization	3.66	A/H
4.	I feel 'emotionally attached to this organization	3.69	A/H
5.	This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	3.85	A/H
6.	I feel a strong sense of belonging to this organization	3.62	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.72	A/H
B. Continuance Commitment			
1.	It would be very hard for me to leave my job at this organization right now even if I wanted to	3.72	A/H
2.	Too much of my life would be disrupted if I left my organization	3.40	A/H
3.	Right now, staying with my job at this organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire	3.59	A/H
4.	I believe I have too few options to consider leaving this organization	3.56	A/H
5.	One of the few negative consequences of leaving my job at this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives elsewhere.	3.45	A/H
6.	One of the major reasons I continue to work for this organization is that leaving would require considerable personal sacrifice	3.58	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.55	A/H
C. Normative Commitment			
1.	I must remain with my organization.	3.62	A/H
2.	Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave.	3.56	A/H
3.	I would feel guilty if I left this organization now 1 2 3 4 5	3.63	A/H
4.	This organization deserves my loyalty	3.76	A/H
5.	I would not leave my organization right now because of my sense of obligation to it	3.73	A/H
6.	I owe a great deal to this organization.	3.82	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.68	A/H
OVERALL MEAN		3.65	

Source: Allan and Meyer (1990), cited by Abdullah, (2011)

Legend:

<i>Range of Mean Values</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	
3.41-4.20	
2.61-3.40	
1.81-2.60	
1.00-1.80	

Overall, employees demonstrated a mean organizational commitment rating of 3.65, interpreted as "agree/high," indicating a moderate to high level of commitment. Affective commitment reflects employees' willingness to devote themselves to the organization, finding purpose in their affiliation. Continuance commitment is driven by a sense of obligation and limited alternatives, impacting employees' decisions to stay. Normative commitment arises from a sense of duty and loyalty to the organization, regardless of personal gain. While affective commitment positively influences job performance, the impact of continuance commitment is debatable, and normative commitment may

lead to decreased well-being (Sinaga et al., 2019; Ardiansyah & Afandi, 2018; Kasogela, 2019; Koskei & Bogonko, 2018; Vanderberghe et al., 2015).

Problem 3: What is the individual work performance of employees?

Table 3. Individual work performance of employees (n=120)

	INDIVIDUAL WORK PERFORMANCE	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
A. Task Performance			
1.	I managed to plan my work so that it was done on time	4.06	A/H
2.	My planning was optimal	3.92	A/H
3.	I kept in mind the results that I had to achieve in my work	4.00	A/H
4.	I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work	4.06	A/H
5.	I knew how to set the right priorities	4.08	A/H
6.	I was able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort	3.96	A/H
	Composite Mean	4.01	A/H
B. Contextual Performance			
1.	I took on extra responsibilities	4.06	A/H
2.	I started a new task myself when my old ones were finished	3.92	A/H
3.	I took on a challenging work task, when available	3.98	A/H
4.	I worked at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date	3.97	A/H
5.	I worked at keeping my job skills up-to-date	3.98	A/H
6.	I came up with creative solutions to new problems	3.98	A/H
7.	I kept looking for new challenges in my job	4.02	A/H
8.	I did more than was expected of me	3.93	
9.	I actively participated in work meetings	3.98	A/H
10.	I actively look for ways to improve my performance at work	3.96	A/H
11.	I grasped opportunities when they presented themselves	3.98	A/H
12.	I knew how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly	3.77	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.96	A/H
C. Counter Productive Behavior			
1.	I complained about unimportant matters at work	2.04	A/H
2.	I made problems greater than they were at work	1.92	A/H
3.	I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects	1.80	A/H
4.	I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work	1.93	A/H
5.	I spoke with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work	1.86	A/H
6.	I did less than was expected of me	1.82	A/H

7.	I managed to get off from a work task easily	1.94	A/H
8.	I sometimes did nothing, when I should have been working	1.80	A/H
	Composite Mean	1.88	A/H
	OVERALL MEAN	3.28	

Source: Koopmans, et al., (2011).

Employees' overall work performance, comprising task, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior, yielded mean scores of 4.01, 3.96, and 1.88, respectively. These scores suggest high levels of task and contextual performance, with minimal counterproductive behavior. Regarding task performance, employees prioritize tasks efficiently, resulting in timely completion. Studies indicate that high task performance contributes to job satisfaction (Veeraragavan & Arulkumar, 2021; Aslan et al., 2022). Contextual performance involves employees taking on additional responsibilities, staying updated, problem-solving creatively, and active participation. Contextual performance is crucial alongside task performance for overall work performance improvement and organizational culture enhancement (Diaz-Vella et al., 2015; Nini, 2019). Counterproductive behavior is minimal, indicating a correlation with high task and contextual performance levels.

Problem 4. Is there a relationship between age and organizational commitment?

The correlation analysis revealed a significant positive relationship ($r = .431, p < .01$) between employees' age and their affective commitment to the institution. This indicates that as employees grow older, their emotional attachment to the organization increases. However, age did not show a significant correlation with continuance commitment ($r = .028$) or normative commitment ($r = .127$), with obtained r values lower than the tabular values at a .05 level of significance. Thus, age differences do not account for variations in employees' continuance and normative commitment levels, which remain consistent across age groups.

Table 4. Correlation coefficients obtained on the test of the relationship between the age and organizational

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT		AGE
Affective Commitment	r	.431**
	(Sig. 2 - tailed)	.000
Continuance Commitment	r	.028
	(Sig. 2-tailed)	.764
Normative Commitment	r	.127
	(Sig. 2-tailed)	.167

** Significant at .01 level of significance (2-tailed)

Problem 5. Is there a relationship between age and individual work performance?

The age of the employees is not significantly related to their work performance in terms of task performance ($r = .129$), contextual performance ($r = .155$), and counterproductive behaviour ($r = -.141$), respectively. The findings denote that the age of the employees has nothing to do with their work performance. Therefore, the variations observed in the individual work performance of the employees are not due to their age differences.

Table 5. Correlation coefficients obtained on the test of relationships between the age and individual work performance of the employees at Divine Word College of Laoag (n= 120)

INDIVIDUAL WORK PERFORMANCE		AGE
Task Performance	r	.129
	(Sig. 2 - tailed)	.161
Contextual Performance	r	.155
	(Sig. 2-tailed)	.091
Counter Productive Behavior	r	-.141
	(Sig. 2-tailed)	.124

* Significant at .01 level of significance (2-tailed)

Results and Discussions

The study aimed to assess the impact of age on organizational commitment and individual work performance. Results revealed a positive correlation between age and affective commitment, suggesting that older employees exhibit greater emotional attachment to the institution. However, no significant correlations were found between age and continuance or normative commitment, indicating that age does not account for variance in these commitment dimensions. Additionally, there was no correlation between age and individual work performance, suggesting that other organizational factors may influence performance outcomes.

The observed relationship between age and affective commitment underscores the importance of fostering employee loyalty and motivation as they age within the organization. Strategies to promote longevity among employees may extend beyond financial incentives to encompass improvements in work environment and leadership practices, as suggested by Sinaga et al. (2019) and Ardiansyah and Afandi (2018).

Conclusion

The institution's workforce predominantly consists of young employees aged between 25 and 35. Regarding age's influence on organizational commitment and individual work performance, the results indicate a correlation with affective commitment but not with continuance and normative commitment. Additionally, there is no correlation between age and individual work performance. Overall, age shows no consistent correlation with organizational commitment and individual work performance, except for affective commitment, where older employees tend to exhibit stronger emotional attachment to the institution.

Authors' contribution.

Authors' Contribution: Conceptualization: D.A., F.P.J., A.R., E.F.A.A, B.P.A.**Methodology:** D.A. F.P.J. B.P.A. **Data collection:** A.R. E., F.A.A. B.P.A. **Formal Analysis:** D.A. F.P.J. A.R. **Writing-Review and Editing:** D.A. F.P.J. F. A.A., B.P.A.

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